

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab

Social Network Analysis from the ESiIL Summit

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Introduction

The [2023 ESIL Innovation Summit](#) was held in person at the University of Colorado on May 23-25, 2023. This first ESIL Summit brought together over 175 participants from around the world and included partners from a variety of sectors including (but not limited to) universities, government agencies, tech companies, Tribal organizations, and research institutions. Over the course of the Summit, participants attended plenary talks and breakout sessions and engaged in networking opportunities. Partners had the opportunity to participate in-person or remotely.

The goals of the 2023 ESIL summit were to:

- Define a decadal research agenda for the growing field of environmental data science by articulating the most pressing environmental challenges and opportunities for solutions-oriented science, and by bridging environmental and biological sciences, social sciences, and data and computational sciences
- Build a diverse and inclusive ESIL network by establishing collaborations with others from different disciplines, sectors, career stages, and backgrounds around research themes of interest

Network Analysis

Social network analysis (SNA) was used to characterize the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. SNA allowed us to study the second of these two goals and evaluate the ESIL network more broadly. The evaluation team analyzed the personal networks of participants at the Innovation Summit to gather baseline information about the newly developing ESIL network and begin to characterize the connections among various partners in ESIL. The Innovation Summit provided a great opportunity to evaluate the ESIL network because it brought together ESIL leadership and existing partners within the environmental data science community while also intentionally invited other EDS leaders and EDS professionals and future ESIL community members to build an inclusive community committed to open science, diverse teams and community-driven approaches to data science. Thus, the evaluation team identified the Innovation Summit participants as reflective of the ESIL network and will survey Innovation Summit participants each year to gather network data to answer the evaluation questions about the network (see evaluation question right).

How has ESIL grown the environmental data science community and expanded its connections (e.g., through building connections between fields and existing networks and bringing in new people and organizations)?

Executive Summary

Network characteristics

The ESIIIL Innovation Summit brought together a variety of people and organizations engaged in Environmental Data Science – **The basis of the ESIIIL network.**

The network analysis identified **over 400 people and 200+ organizations** that currently comprise the ESIIIL network.

Members of the ESIIIL leadership team are the **most centralized** to the network. They connect people and organizations across the network and can disseminate information across the network effectively.

NEON (National Ecological Observatory Network) and University of Colorado Boulder are currently the **most central organizations** in the ESIIIL network.

The **Environmental Data Science (EDS) roles and research connections** are the largest and most prevalent dimension of the ESIIIL network.

Connections through communication are **well-developed** throughout the network.

Advocates for communities underrepresented in EDS and members of communities underrepresented in EDS are a **small but well-connected dimension** of the ESIIIL network.

Participants at the Summit indicated making a number of **new connections**

Suggestions for Use of Network Data

- Use lists of people and organizations identified as part of the network analysis as a **tool for recruitment** for future ESIIIL events and activities.
- Identify **areas of focus for connection building** across people and organizations in the network by inviting participation from a greater diversity of professional roles within EDS and ways in which they can collaborate with one another.
- Provide baseline characteristics of the ESIIIL network to compare against in future to **measure growth in network size and connectivity.**

*"Collaboration" by Eko Purnomo, "Network" by Desi Aulia, "Network" by Iakonicon, "Organization" by Soremba, "Research" by Eucalyp, "Communication" by Creative Stall pk, "connected" by Travis Avery, "summit" by Kemesh Maharjan np all from the [Noun Project](#).

Methods

Survey Design

Determining participant roles

Summit participants were asked to select what role(s) they play in the field of environmental data science (see role options right). Survey respondents were presented with the following definition as they were answering the question: *Environmental Data Science (EDS) includes any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions, and science to understand our environment. It is highly trans-disciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.*

The list of roles in the EDS field was generated by ESIL leadership based on communities they had identified as key partners to ESIL (see below). The roles were categorized into two groups: roles that were EDS-specific and roles that were non-EDS specific (which included advocates and members of communities underrepresented in EDS and students).

Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS). Select all that apply.

- People working in Environmental, Biological, Social Science field
- People working in Computational and/or Data Science field
- Data provider
- (Data science) Educator
- Application partner
- Industry representative
- Synthesis center member
- Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Analytics professional
- Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations
- Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations
- Student
- Other. Please describe.

ESIL Network

Identifying connections

Summit participants were asked to identify their connections to other individuals and organizations within the work that they do around Environmental Data Science (EDS), to characterize the person-person connections and person-organization connections. For each of these two options, respondents were able to report up to 20 connections.

For those who self-identified as one or more of the EDS-specific roles, they were provided with structured connection questions. This meant they could see a suggested list of individuals and organizations - textboxes provided for these responses would autocomplete with the names and organizations of current ESIIIL partners and those people and organizations in attendance at the Summit to reduce errors in spelling and to assist with recall (see autocomplete example upper right). They were also provided with a link to a list of ESIIIL partners and Summit participants and organizations if they preferred to reference the list as a whole and to reduce recall bias (see reference list of people lower right). Survey respondents were not limited to the autocomplete options and had the ability to write in names and organizations not included on the reference list.

In contrast, respondents with only non-EDS-specific roles were given open-ended question structures for their connections (see below). This design was chosen based on the assumption that this group of participants may collaborate with more individuals or organizations not currently connected to the general EDS or ESIIIL community, and that their types of collaborations may also be more diverse than those listed for EDS respondents. The evaluation team decided that providing open-ended responses could reduce the risk of creating a sense of exclusion for non-EDS respondents and potentially omit responses that may not be reflected in the structured options.

ESIIIL
Personal connection #1:

Emilia Williams
Emiley Eloe-Fadrosch
Emily Biggane
Emily Pastewka
Emily Ward
Mahmoud Abouelmakarem
Nate Emery
Ruben Remelgado

	A	B	C
1	Abby Benson		
2	Abigail Toretsky		
3	Adam Newman		
4	Adam Samazin		
5	Al Kuslikis		
6	Alex Barth		
7	Alexa Azure		
8	Alexander Yoshizumi		
9	Alicia Foxx		

	First and Last Name(s)	Nature of Collaboration
Personal Connection #1	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Personal Connection #2	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Determining the nature of collaborations

For each connection identified, respondents were required to identify the nature of the collaboration with the individual or organization. For those with EDS-specific roles, they were provided with a list of eight types of collaborations from which to select (see options right). They were also given the option to input open-ended responses in each case. Those respondents with non-EDS-specific were not provided with the structured list but rather were able to describe the nature of their collaboration as an open-ended response.

Data Cleaning and Analysis

Data were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. All social network analysis was completed in the online social network analysis program [Kumu](#), an online platform for mapping networks and systems.

Open-ended responses to the “nature of collaboration” questions were coded manually by labeling them as one or more of the broad categories (Research, Resources, Interpersonal Communications, Professional Community). The codes were decided based on a response’s similarity or agreement to any of the response options within each category. The most common open-ended responses included Research collaborations (such as presenting on panels or having an advisor/advisee relationship), Interpersonal Communications collaborations (such as knowing another individual as an organization’s representative or from a shared working group), and Professional Community collaborations (such as being co-workers with another individual).

Once responses were coded, the data spreadsheet was cleaned and restructured using R code, in preparation for upload to the SNA program Kumu. Cleaning entailed identifying spelling mistakes or duplicate responses with different spellings, and modifying them to a corrected and unique spelling, as well as assigning sub-categories of responses to the four broader categories (i.e. assigning survey option 1 - Ongoing Research to the category Research).

After cleaning, the data was restructured into a list of connections (detailing the two people connected, the direction of the connection, and the categories it falls under) and a list of nodes (detailing the ID and corresponding information for each person and organization in the network). The two lists were used as inputs in Kumu to create the network maps.

Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with (Select all that apply.)*

- Ongoing research
- Grant proposals for future research
- Co-author on papers
- Collaboration on data products
- Collaboration on code or software tools
- Collaboration on educational materials
- Preliminary discussions
- Learning
- Other (please explain)

Network Maps

The social network maps below represent the responses from 164 ESIL Innovation Summit participants. In the maps, the circles are called “nodes,” representing individual people and organizations who took the survey and/or were named as collaborators. The lines in between the circles represent a “tie” or “connection” between the nodes, in this case when a survey respondent mentioned that they collaborated with a specific person or organization. For these maps, ties do not have a direction; instead, if one person identified a collaboration with another, then we considered the collaboration as reciprocated. The position of the nodes is mapped in the circular format by default. This default configuration was kept for all the following maps for easy visual comparison of connections between the whole network maps and maps of network dimensions.

For future analysis (and in subsequent years of data collection), the node position can be manipulated to more easily visualize areas of connection density and identify “bridges” - people or organizations that tie two different groups of the network together. Individual nodes (i.e. isolates) - people who took the survey but did not identify any connections - and small unconnected groups within the network (constellations) are also useful data points in the network analysis.

Effective management of the network can be measured through these indicators. If managed well, these network components become more connected/centralized over time, particularly if the nodes represent people who indicated that their roles were related to members of underrepresented groups in EDS. The following maps represent the state of the ESIL network at the time of the 2023 Innovation Summit.

(Note: Numbers are used to identify people and organizations. Due to IRB protocol, the identity of individual people is protected through the use of an unidentifiable number in the maps. A list of all organizations depicted in the networks and their corresponding identification number is included in the Appendix.)

ESiIL Network Maps

People and Organizations within the ESiIL Network

Figure 1: Network map of the ESiIL network including both people (blue nodes; n=430) and organizations (yellow nodes; n=223). **Thicker lines connecting nodes indicate more developed collaborations.** Yellow rectangle shows area depicted in Figure 1a.

The whole network map (Fig. 1) represents all respondents to the survey (n=164) and as well as all the people (n=430) and organizations (n=223) the respondents identified as connections. The whole

network map provides a full picture of the ESIL network at the time of the 2023 ESIL summit. Lines between nodes show where connections exist between people and/or organizations and the thickness of the line represents the different types of connections that are present between nodes. As described in the methods section above, the nature of the connection categories can be grouped according to connections made through research, resources, interpersonal communication and professional community. The thicker lines represent connections that span more than one of these connection categories. The thickest lines between nodes indicate that the connections are defined by all four nature of the connection categories and thus are considered more diverse (and potentially more developed) connection types.

Figure 1a: Enlarged area of Figure 1 to show the detail of the personal and organizational connections.

In the enlarged area of the whole network map, the connections among people and organizations can be seen more clearly. Each person and organization is labeled with a numerical identifier. In this area of the network, note that person 127 has multiple connections to other people (blue nodes) and a handful of organizations (yellow nodes). The nature of person 127’s connections vary, with some spanning research, resource, communication and professional community categories (thickest lines, ex: 127-113) and while other connections are more focused within one or two of the nature of collaboration categories (thin lines, ex: 127-153). The personal and organizational network of 127 is connected to other personal and organizational networks within ESIL. For example, person 127’s relationship with organization 541 (NCEAS (National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis)), connects them to other people in the ESIL network (ex: 302). This offers just one example of how people are connected within the ESIL network and the sum of these direct and indirect connections produce the web of the ESIL network depicted in Figure 1.

People in the ESIL Network

Figure 2: Map of personal connections within the ESIL network. Yellow nodes (n=164) represent people who completed the survey while blue nodes (n=488) represent people identified as connections within the network but who did not complete the survey themselves. **Larger nodes have more connections and thicker connecting lines indicate more numerous connection types.**

The people network for Innovation Summit participants (Fig. 2) represents the 164 people who responded to the survey (indicated in yellow) and people they named as connections who did not respond to the survey (blue). The size of the node reflects the degree centrality for that node, meaning that the person has a higher number of connections relative to the others (see Table 2).

In this map, the thickness of the line between nodes represents a greater number of connection types. In this depiction, rather than representing the broad categories of connection described in the previous slide (e.g., research, resource, interpersonal communication, and professional community), the thickness is representative of the total number of connection types (up to 8 different “nature of the

connection” options were provided in the survey. For those who provided the connection nature in open-ended textboxes, connections were binned into these categories). These eight different connection types were then grouped under the categories of research, resource, communication and professional community categories more broadly.

Table 1. Whole ESIL network statistics

	# Nodes	# Connections	Average Degree	Density
People and Organizations	653	1027	3.15	0.0048
People	430	567	2.64	0.0061

Overall, the network statistics for the people and organizations of the ESIL network and those for the people within ESIL provide baseline metrics that broadly characterize the network (Table 1). The social network analysis measures of interest for the baseline ESIL network are:

- 1) number of nodes, the total number of people or organizations in the network;
- 2) number of connections, the total number of reported connections between people/organizations in the network;
- 3) average degree, the average number of connections per person/organization; and
- 4) density, the number of connections as a proportion to the number of connections possible.

As expected, the people and organizational network within the ESIL community has a greater number of nodes and connections than the people network alone. These values are used to calculate the density of each of the networks. The people network is slightly denser than the network of people and organizations but both networks have low density given that the networks both have isolates (e.g. nodes without any connections). The people and organizational network is more connected (3.15 average connections per node) than the people network alone which has, on average, 2.64 connections per node. While these numbers do not tell us anything new about how the whole network compares to the personal network (e.g. people and organizations have more nodes than the personal network and thus have more connections), these metrics will be useful in determining how those networks are changing each year (e.g. compare growth, level of connectivity, etc.). For example, we might expect to see the number of nodes and connections grow each year, as well as see higher average degree centrality and network density as relationships among people and organizations within ESIL develop over time.

Personal network statistics for ESIL

Centrality measures

Table 2 lists the top ten nodes (people or organizations) with the highest centrality within the ESIL network. Common social network analysis centrality measures include:

- 1) Degree centrality (the measure of the number of connections for a node),
 - 2) Closeness centrality (the normalized distance* each node is from all other nodes in the network),
- and

3) Betweenness centrality (the number of times a node falls along the shortest path between two other nodes) (Borgatti et al, 2018).

Each centrality measure provides different information for each node. Degree centrality helps to understand the structural importance of individual nodes within the network (Borgatti et al. 2018). In general, nodes with high degree centrality are the local connectors/hubs within the network but are not necessarily the best connected across the wider network. Nodes with high closeness can spread information to the rest of the network most easily and usually have high visibility into what is happening across the network because of their proximity to other nodes within the network. Nodes with high betweenness centrality have more control over the flow of information and act as bridges within the network (or potential points of failure) because of their position between nodes. **The distance is calculated by counting the number of connections composing the shortest path between nodes and then normalized by dividing that value (n) into n-1.*

For the ESiIL network, the nodes with highest centrality are shown below in Table 2. In terms of degree centrality, all ten of the top nodes are associated with the ESiIL leadership team with the top three people have over 40 connections among them (either that they identified themselves or that were identified by others who completed the survey). Figure 3 visually represents the degree centrality among the top people (blue squares) and organizations (yellow squares) within the network, however, no organizations make the top 10.

Table 2: Top 10 people and organizations with the greatest number of connections, closeness and betweenness centrality. People are shown in non-bold font, organizations are shown in bold and people outside of the ESiIL leadership in orange italics font.

	Node ID	Degree Centrality	Node ID	Closeness Centrality	Node ID	Betweenness Centrality
#1	413	49	413	0.261	413	0.104
#2	194	48	186	0.258	186	0.094
#3	186	44	411	0.241	543	0.079
#4	313	38	82	0.236	82	0.058
#5	411	37	194	0.230	411	0.045
#6	93	28	93	0.229	615	0.044
#7	335	23	204	0.229	<i>214</i>	0.042
#8	82	22	543	0.227	<i>293</i>	0.042
#9	204	22	615	0.224	<i>371</i>	0.041
#10	91	22	91	0.222	194	0.035

Figure 3: Nodes with the greatest degree centrality in the ESIL network. Blue squares represent people and yellow squares represent organizations with **high degree centrality** within the network.

In terms of closeness centrality, again, all but two (bold) are members of the ESIL leadership team. Identifiers 543 and 615 represent the organizations NEON (National Ecological Observatory Network) and University of Colorado Boulder respectively. There is more diversity in terms of who are the important bridges of information within the ESIL network. Five of the top ten nodes with high betweenness centrality are members of the ESIL leadership team, the National Ecological Observatory Network and University of Colorado Boulder are seen to be key bridges as well. Three of the ten top nodes of betweenness are people outside of the research team. These centrality measures characterize how individual nodes fit within the larger network and it makes sense that at this early stage of ESIL those with high centrality are within the leadership team and associated with organizations with strong ties to the ESIL leaders. Over time and growth of ESIL, we should see centrality measures should increase for people and organizations across a larger portion of the network.

Network Dimensions

Personal Role

ESIL summit participants self-identified what role(s) they have within the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS). The roles fall into two groups: roles that are EDS-specific and roles that are not EDS-specific (which include advocates and members from communities underrepresented in EDS and students). We can view these role categories as network dimensions and compare them to one another with respect to their size and density. For comparison, Figures 4-7 represent social network maps of the people with EDS-specific roles, non-EDS specific roles, those engaged with/representatives of communities underrepresented within EDS, and students. In these maps, survey respondents and their connections are depicted. Thicker lines connecting nodes indicate a greater number of connection types (e.g. span different categories of connection nature) and/or multiple connections within a single connection category.

Table 3. Roles within the field of Environmental Data Science with number of people selecting those roles (n).

EDS-specific roles	Non-EDS-specific roles
People working in Environmental, Biological, Social Science field (n=136)	Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations (n=31)
People working in Computational and/or Data Science field (n=69)	Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations (n=25)
Data provider (n=28)	Student (n=35)
(Data science) Educator (n=87)	Other (n=2)
Application partner (n=9)	
Industry representative (n=2)	
Synthesis center member (n=23)	
Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Analytics professional (n=24)	

Figure 4: Map of people with EDS-specific roles. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are light blue. Qualitatively, the **EDS-specific dimension of the ESIL network is nearly identical to the personal networks** displayed in the whole network map. In general, **nodes with high degree centrality tend to have the greatest number of connection types** as well.

Figure 5: Map of people that are in non-EDS-specific roles. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are light blue. In general, the non-EDS role dimension shows a similar pattern to the whole network map and EDS-specific dimension in the lower half of the map, with closely spaced nodes and numerous connections. However, there are **fewer nodes present in the upper half of the map** than in Fig 4 and **more unidimensional connections** (those that fall under only one type of connection).

Figure 6: Map of people who advocate for or described that they come from communities underrepresented in EDS. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are light blue. As with other maps, **the thicker lines connecting nodes indicate a greater number of connection types and can be found primarily among nodes in the lower half of the map for nodes of high degree centrality.** Both nodes and connections are reduced in this map overall, with fewer nodes and connections present in the upper half of the map. Connection types are limited to one or two types of connections.

Figure 7: Map of student population. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are light blue. Student nodes and connections tend to **make isolated “constellations”** that have limited connectivity across the network. Within constellations, **students are connected in multiple ways**, often identifying five or more different types of connections with other students.

Overall the network of people in EDS-specific roles are more numerous and have more connections than those in non-EDS-specific roles in the entire ESIIIL network. In the maps of both dimensions, connections are more numerous between people who are central to the network (e.g. ESIIIL leadership), but also connect nodes more broadly across the network. Connections range from more unidimensional (thin lines of connection, connected only by a single activity) to more developed (thick lines of connection, connected by a range of activities). The maps depicting the advocates for/members of communities underrepresented in EDS dimension and student dimensions show more limited reach across the network, again tied more closely to ESIIIL leadership members than to the entire network. Where connections exist between members within these communities, they appear to be more developed (e.g. thick connection lines) both with people more central the network and/or within their isolated constellations of connections (See Network Statistics).

Types of Collaboration

ESIIIL summit participants were asked to define the nature of their connections to other people by selecting from a list of nine different types of collaboration that were identified by the ESIIIL leadership team. The nature of the connections falls into four groups (see below) and can be viewed as additional network dimensions to compare to one another and to the dimensions by role in terms of their size and density. The “other” category allowed participants to describe the nature of their connection and these answers were binned into one of the four broad categories below.

Table 4. Categories for different types of connections with number of people with those connection types (n).

Research Connections (n=303)	Resource Connections (n=254)	Interpersonal Connections (n=212)	Professional Community Connections (n=47)
Ongoing research	Collaboration on data products	Preliminary discussions	Learning
Grant proposals for future research	Collaboration on code or software tools	Other (ex. potential collaborator)	Other (ex. Co-worker, employer)
Co-author on papers	Collaboration on educational materials		
Other (ex. presentations/panels)			

The following maps display these dimensions of the larger ESIIIL network as it relates to the nature of the connections that people have with one another (Figures 8-11). In these maps, all people (both survey respondents and named collaborators) are depicted in each dimension. Connections among survey respondents and their named collaborators are displayed according to connection category and connections are depicted by lines of equal thickness.

Figure 8: Map of Research Connections. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are light blue. This map showcases the research connections only. **Research connections are the most prevalent type of connection that survey respondents selected to describe the nature of their connection to others in their personal networks.** Research connections span across the network map.

Figure 9: Map of Resource Connections. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are light blue. This map showcases the resource connections only. **Fewer people identified connections that are related to collaboration on resources** (software, code, educational materials, etc.). Resource connections are **more concentrated** in the lower half of the map near nodes of high centrality (See Fig. 2) with a few isolated constellations in more distal areas of the network.

Figure 10: Map of Interpersonal Communication Connections. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are light blue. This map showcases interpersonal communication connections only. **People identified numerous connections related to interpersonal communication whether it be through preliminary discussion on a project or idea or through contacting potential collaborators.** These connections are **denser** in the lower half of the map near the nodes with high centrality, however, these types of connections also span across different zones of the network, albeit with less frequency than the research connections seen in Fig. 8.

Figure 11: Map of Professional Community Connections. This category of connection type has the fewest connections **relative to the entire network**, though the connections **present do span across the entire dimension network**. The low frequency may be related to the survey instrument – only “learning” was a response option for people to select – and the other professional community connections were identified from coding the open-ended responses. These open responses identified co-workers and employers with whom they are not necessarily working on research or resources. In future network survey questions, we will provide participants with additional options of professional community connections from which to choose.

Network statistics

Overall network trends across dimensions for all ESIL community members

Table 5. SNA measures of the network across dimensions of the ESIL’s personal networks

	# Nodes	# Connections	Average Degree	Density
People in EDS-specific roles	378	556	2.65	0.0078
People in Non-EDS-specific roles	93	316	2.76	0.0739
People who advocate for/are from groups underrepresented in EDS	56	259	3.26	0.1682
Students	35	94	1.71	0.1580
People with research connections	303	366	2.42	0.0122
People with resource connections	254	300	2.36	0.0098
People in communication with others	212	280	2.64	0.0116
People with contacts within their professional community	47	38	1.62	0.0870

When comparing networks for the four role dimensions to each other, the networks for people in EDS-specific roles is by far the largest (378 nodes), followed by the non-EDS specific roles, advocates and people underrepresented in EDS, and student role dimensions. The most developed (e.g. connected) dimension network is that for the people who advocate for or are from groups underrepresented in EDS which has an average of 3.26 connections among people in its network; whereas the EDS-specific and non-EDS-specific role dimensions networks have only an average of 2.65 connections and 2.76 connections respectively. The student role dimension is the least developed at 1.71 connections on average (see Average Degree measure in Table 5). Network density is greatest among advocates for/underrepresented groups in EDS, followed by students, people in non-EDS-specific roles, and people in EDS-specific roles. Taken together (average degree and density metrics), there is greater collaboration among people within the advocates for/underrepresented group role dimension than for the other dimensions even though it is one of the smaller networks. The student role dimension is also a small, high density network, but has less connectivity relatively (e.g. smaller average degree value). Both the student role and advocates/underrepresented role dimensions comprise the larger non-EDS role dimension. While there is collaboration within these smaller network dimensions, there is room for growth in connectivity across roles which would be reflected in the EDS-specific and non-EDS specific role dimensions.

When comparing dimensions by connection type, the research dimension is the most common connection of ESIL community members, followed by the resource, communications, and professional community dimension networks (see Table 5). The research, resource and communication dimension networks are relatively similar in terms of their connectivity (2.42, 2.36 and 2.64 average degree), but the research and communications connection dimensions have greater density indicating greater collaboration among the nodes in these dimensions. The least prevalent connection type is professional community connections. While this connection type connects the fewest people in the network, those who have this type of connection have the greatest density among the different connection type dimensions. Overall, the greatest collaboration among the network dimensions is within the research and communication dimensions with room for growth within the resource connection and professional community dimension.

Impact of the Innovation Summit on Network Connections

Innovation Summit participants responded to a reflection survey which included questions that were intended to measure the impact of the Summit on network connections. When reflecting on how many connections they made during the summit, the majority of respondents made between 1 and 6 new connections as a result of the summit, while about a third of the participants indicated having made 7 to 10+ new connections. When asked to elaborate on those new connections, respondents noted meeting individuals and connecting with new organizations as well as becoming part of new, interdisciplinary working groups and having conversations around shared ideas and/or topics.

How many new connections or research collaborations have you made during the Summit? (n=118)

Interpretations

The network survey questions embedded in the ESIL Innovation Summit survey gathered important social network data to **help characterize the people and organizations that are the basis for the ESIL network**. In addition to determining the size of the whole network (people and organizations) and quantifying connections among nodes in the network, social network analysis allows for visualizing the network and the patterns of organization among different dimensions within the larger network. Centrality metrics describe how each node fits within the larger network and network density is an indicator for how connected the nodes are within the network, a good proxy for collaboration among people and organizations.

Overall, the number of people and organizations comprising these early stages of the ESIL network is large (400+ people and 200+ organizations). The network density values highlight the opportunity for greater connectivity across the people and organizations in this first year of the network. ESIL Summit participants who completed the survey identified 257 people with whom they connect with on EDS projects (but who did not respond to the survey themselves) some of which were not known to ESIL as potential collaborators in environmental data science. This information offers an opportunity to broaden the reach of ESIL to new partners and their affiliated institutions. The list of people and organizations named in the network survey alone can serve as a tool for recruitment for other ESIL network events and activities.

Centrality measures for people and organizations indicated the importance of the people and organizations comprising the ESIL leadership team. It makes sense that members of the ESIL leadership team have the largest number of connections per node (e.g. degree centrality) and act as hubs connecting smaller network communities and as information spreaders to others in the network. The ESIL leadership is highly visible to the rest of the network given their proximity to other nodes (e.g. closeness centrality). The leadership team can strengthen the building of connections given their position between nodes in the network, acting as bridges between nodes or groups of nodes across the network. But this also indicates that the network (in these early stages of development) is reliant on members of the ESIL leadership team for connection building. As the ESIL network matures, the network will likely have other people and organizations beyond the ESIL leadership rise to the top 10 or even the top 20 in centrality metrics. This broadening of key contributors will be important for the sustainability of the network and to reach a broader audience which had not yet been included in EDS-focused work.

Analysis of the network dimensions according to personal role and connection type indicates that **EDS-specific roles and research connections are the most predominant dimensions of the ESIL network at this time**. Communication among people in the network is well-developed. Network dimensions such as advocates for groups underrepresented in EDS and those who identify as a member of a group underrepresented in EDS are small but well-connected within that dimension. This connectedness is important in that as this dimension grows over time (given that increasing the diversity of participants

and organizations an overarching goal of ESIL), the additional nodes will be incorporated into an already connected network, potentially facilitating collaborations within the network. Collaborating on resource development is also not as well developed, with smaller constellations of people collaborating with one another. The ESIL team can identify the nodes of high betweenness centrality to help connect these isolated constellations into a more connected network within this dimension. Analysis of the dimensions highlights the areas for the most growth within the network by focusing the attention on developing greater connectivity among nodes.

Assumptions, Limitations, and Next Steps

The social network analysis conducted at the ESIL Innovation Summit provides a snapshot of the larger ESIL network in this early stage of network development. The following assumptions and limitations are important to note: We assumed that ESIL Innovation Summit participants are representative of the EDS community and that survey respondents are representative of the ESIL community and the emerging ESIL network. **The following limitations need to be considered:**

1. We did not get 100% response rate for the pre-survey network questions thus the data were not from of *all* the ESIL Innovation Summit participants.
2. We chose to bound the network using the ESIL Innovation Summit as our sample. We interpret the social network data with this in mind, that these connections represent the ESIL members who attended the Summit.
3. We chose to force symmetry on the connections between nodes in our analysis, which limits our ability to interpret the directionality of the collaborations identified in the network data.

Given these considerations, we will continue to collect data from all ESIL Summit participants each year. In addition, we will invite participants from past Summits, and to those who were named as collaborators by Innovation Summit participants to study network development over time. This strategy will help to ensure that the sample is representative of the network, while also still using the ESIL Innovation Summit as the sampling frame. Further, it will allow us to collect data regarding the directionality of collaborations between people. For example, it would be useful to know if the connection between nodes represented a mutual collaboration or not. The directional data will provide more insight into how information could be disseminated through the larger network and within network dimensions, as well as be an indicator of the strength of collaboration (e.g. mutual connections = stronger collaborations). Furthermore, in subsequent surveys, we will not include ESIL as a potential organization for collaboration. We included ESIL as an option in this baseline network survey because we assumed that the ESIL Innovation Summit participants would be more representative of the EDS community more broadly and not yet identify as ESIL members given that the ESIL network had just started to develop. As ESIL grows, the Innovation Summit likely will have participants that identify as members of ESIL, thus the results of our network analysis should show what other organizations are connected to ESIL through its members (as represented by the current and past Innovation Summit participants). Additional analyses will highlight the people and organizations present across dimensions of the network, and what role organizations play specifically in connecting people within the network.

Conclusions

The social network analysis of the ESIL Innovation Summit data provides a baseline by which data from future analyses can be compared. In particular, social network analysis can help identify how the population of people and organizations within ESIL changes over time, and how collaborations among people and organizations develop. The network analysis highlights the strength of the network in terms of its participants from EDS-specific roles and research collaborations. It also highlights a small, but well-connected group of people who identify as advocates for or from groups underrepresented in EDS. The presence of this dimension within the network likely represents intentional recruitment and relationship building by the ESIL leadership to broaden participation in EDS through ESIL. The results of the network analysis identify opportunities for growth in the ESIL network in order to achieve the goal of “enabling an inclusive community of practice to leverage the wealth of environmental data for challenges in the environmental sciences”.

References

Borgatti, Stephen P., Martin G. Everett, and Jeffrey C. Johnson. *Analyzing social networks*. Sage, 2018.

Appendix A: Network Survey Questions

ESIIIL Innovation Summit participants were selected based on their ability to help build the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community of the future. Understanding the thoughts and opinions of Innovation Summit participants is therefore crucial. Please fill out the information below to the best of your ability.

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.

Please provide your first and last name

Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS). Select all that apply.

- People working in Environmental, Biological, Social Science field (1)
- People working in Computational and/or Data Science field (13)
- Data provider (2)
- (Data science) Educator (3)
- Application partner (4)
- Industry representative (5)
- Synthesis center member (7)
- Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Analytics professional (8)
- Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations (9)
- Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations (10)
- Student (11)
- Other. Please describe. (12) _____

Pre-survey questions

Connections

The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do around Environmental Data Science (EDS). Please include **all** of your connections, not just the ones that may be attending the ESIIIL summit.

We are interested in two types of connections: Personal and Organizational connections.

Personal Connections - With whom do you work on EDS projects?

Organizational Connections - Which organizations do you work with on EDS projects?

Personal Connections Questions

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed

Q8 Please type the full name of the personal connections with whom you currently work on EDS projects (if any) in the text boxes provided.

When you begin typing in the box, you can select from dropdown options* or type in your connection's full name to have it recorded. *Dropdown options are mostly names of participants attending the ESIL summit and thus are not comprehensive of the larger EDS community.

Please add your main EDS connections, these could be only a few or many. You are **not** required to fill all of the textboxes provided.

If you have worked with ESIL members, but cannot remember the full names of people you have worked with, you can view an ESIL reference list [clicking here](#).

##[Question format for EDS-specific role]

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed

Q9 Personal connection #1:

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Display This Question:

If Personal connection #1: Text Response Is Not Empty

Q30 Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with [name of personal connection] (Select all that apply.)*

- Ongoing research (1)
- Grant proposals for future research (2)
- Co-author on papers (3)
- Collaboration on data products (4)
- Collaboration on code or software tools (9)
- Collaboration on educational materials (5)
- Preliminary discussions (6)
- Learning (7)
- Other (please explain) (8) _____

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

##[Question format for non-EDS-specific role]

Start of Block: SNA Personal Connections - General role

Display This Question:

If Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations

Or Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations

Or Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Student

Or Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Other. Please describe.

And If

Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the Environmental Data... Is Displayed

Q121 Please indicate the **people** with whom you currently work with on EDS projects (if any). Type the first and last name into the text boxes provided, and the nature of your collaboration. Please add your main EDS connections, these could be only a few or many. You are **not** required to fill all of the textboxes provided. If you have worked with ESIL members, but cannot remember the full names of people you have worked with, you can view a reference list of the people involved with ESIL by [clicking here](#).

	First and Last Name(s) (1)	Nature of Collaboration (4)
Personal Connection #1 (1)		
Personal Connection #2 (2)		
Personal Connection #3 (3)		
Personal Connection #4 (4)		
Personal Connection #5 (5)		
Personal Connection #6 (6)		
Personal Connection #7 (7)		
Personal Connection #8 (8)		

##[Note: Table rows repeat for connections up to #20]

Organizational Connections

##Both EDS-specific roles and non-EDS-specific roles receive this question format

Please type the **organizations** with whom you currently work with on Environmental Data Science (EDS) projects (if any) in the textboxes provided. When you begin typing in the box, you can select from the dropdown options* or type in your connection's name to have it recorded. *Dropdown options are mostly names of organizations attending the ESIL summit and thus are not comprehensive of the larger EDS community.

Please add your main EDS organizational connections, these could be only a few or many. You are **not** required to fill all of the textboxes provided.

Organizations can include research centers, institutes, universities or academic institutions, networks, private sector partners, nonprofits or other organizations. You can view a reference list of the organizations involved with ESIL by [clicking here](#).

Q128 Organization #1:

Q129 Organization #2:

Q130 Organization #3:

Q131 Organization #4:

Q132 Organization #5:

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Display This Question:

*If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed
And Organization #1: Text Response Is Not Empty*

##[Question format for EDS-specific role]

Q149 Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with **[organization name]** (Select all that apply.)*

- Ongoing research (1)
- Grant proposals for future research (2)
- Co-author on papers (3)
- Collaboration on data products (4)
- Collaboration on code or software tools (9)
- Collaboration on educational materials (5)
- Preliminary discussions (6)
- Learning (7)
- Other (please explain) (8) _____

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the Environmental Data... Is Displayed
And Organization #1: Text Response Is Not Empty

##[Question format for non-EDS-specific role]

Q169 Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with **[organization name]**

[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Q13 Are there people and/or organizations that you currently work with on EDS projects that are not listed here? Please provide the names, organizational affiliations, and the nature of your collaboration.

Post-survey questions

Q61 How many new connections or research collaborations have you made during the Summit?

- 1 to 3 (1)
 - 4 to 6 (2)
 - 7 to 9 (3)
 - 10 or more (4)
 - I did not make (5)
-

Q62 Please elaborate on **the top two** most important or exciting new connections or collaborations you have made during the Summit towards innovation in your work. (Please include the names of people and their affiliations and/or organizations where appropriate)

Appendix B: Lists of Organizations and People

Organization	Identification number
AAG (American Association of Geographers)	420
AGU (American Geophysical Union)	421
AI for Conservation Slack Community	422
AIHEC (American Indian Higher Education Consortium)	423
Allen Institute for AI	424
Amazon Environmental Research Institute	425
AmeriFlux	426
Arctic Data Center	427
Arizona State University	428
Atlas of Living Australia	429
Australian Research Data Commons	430
Axiom Data Science	431
Battelle	432
Baylor University	433
BEDE Network	434
Biocultural Diversity Lab at Colorado State University	435
Biodiversity Collections Network	436
Boston University	437
Bren School of Environmental Science and Management	438
CALeDNA	439
Chicago Botanic Garden	440
CIRES (Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences)	441
Clean Water 4 All Coalition	442
Clemson University	443
Climate Change AI	444
Climate Informatics	445
CODATA	446
College of the Muscogee Nation	447
Colorado State University	448
Cornell Lab Of Ornithology	449
County Government of Nyamira	450
Critical Zone Network	451
CUAHSI (Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science, Inc.)	452
CV4Ecology	453
CyVerse	454
CZNet	455
Deloitte	456
Delta Science Program	457
Denver Botanic Gardens	458
Drexel University	459

Dynamic Water Critical Zone	460
Earth Lab	461
Ecological Forecasting Initiative	462
Ecological Society of America (ESA)	463
EDSIN (Environmental Data Science Inclusion Network)	464
Environment and Climate Change Canada	465
Environmental Data Initiative	466
Environmental Data Science journal	467
Environmental Defense Fund (EDF)	468
Environmental Policy Innovation Center	469
EREN (Ecological Research as Education Network)	470
eScience Institute	471
ESIIL (Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab)	472
ESIP (Earth Science Information Partners)	473
Florida Department of Health	474
Florida Medical Entomology Laboratory	475
Florida Museum	476
GEO BON	477
GEO Indigenous Alliance	478
German Aerospace Center - DLR	479
Getches-Wilkinson Center for Natural Resources, Energy, and the Environment	480
GGBN (Global Genome Biodiversity Network)	481
Google	482
Great Lakes Bioenergy Research Center	483
Harvard University	484
Haskell Indian Nations University	485
Haskell Indian Nations University - Sensing the Earth	486
Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ	487
Holden Arboretum	488
ICAR-National Rice Research Institute, India	489
iDigBio	490
iDiv (German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research)	491
IIASA (International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis)	492
Indian Council of Agricultural Research	493
Indigenous Peoples Climate Change Working Group	494
Insectarium of Montreal	495
INSTAAR (Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research)	496
Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research (IMK)- KIT	497
James Cook University	498
Kansas University	499
Keweenaw Bay Ojibwa College	500
Lakota Atlas	501
Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory	502
Livelihoods Knowledge Exchange Network	503

Long Term Agroecosystem Research Network	504
Los Alamos National Laboratory	505
Louisiana State Water Chemistry Department	506
LTER (Long Term Ecological Research Network)	507
Marquette University	508
Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)	509
MEFA (Macrosystems Ecology For All) Research Coordination Network	510
Metropolitan State University of Denver	511
Michigan State University	512
Microsoft Corporation	513
MIDAS (Michigan Institute for Data Science)	514
NASA	515
NASA Earth Science Data Systems	516
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center	517
NASA Harvest	518
NASA JPL	519
National Center for Disease Control Georgia	520
National Computational Infrastructure (NCI - Australia)	521
National Interagency Fire Center	522
National Phenology Network	523
National Wildfire Coordinating Group	524
Native BioData Consortium	525
Navajo Technical University	526
NCAR (National Center for Atmospheric Research)	527
NCASC (National Climate Adaptation Science Center)	528
NCEAS (National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis)	529
NCEP (National Centers for Environmental Prediction)	530
NEON (National Ecological Observatory Network)	531
Network for Integrated Agricultural Resilience Research	532
NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration)	533
NOAA Climate & Global Change Postdoctoral Fellowship	534
NOAA GSL (Global Systems Laboratory)	535
NOAA NCAS-M (Cooperative Science Center in Atmospheric Sciences and Meteorology)	536
NOAA NCEI (National Centers for Environmental Information)	537
North Carolina Institute for Climate Studies	538
Northern Arizona University	539
Northern Illinois University	540
Northern Jaguar Project	541
Northwestern University	542
NSF (National Science Foundation)	543
Ocean Vision AI	544
Oglala Lakota College	545
Ohio State University	546
Open Knowledge Nepal	547

Oregon State University	548
Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	549
Penn State University	550
PhenoCam Network	551
Planet Labs	552
Polar Geospatial Center	553
Princeton University	554
Project Red Bus	555
Purdue University	556
pyOpenSci	557
Pyrologix LLC/Vibrant Planet	558
Queensland University of Technology	559
RDA (Research Data Alliance)	560
Rio de Janeiro Botanical Garden	561
RISCC	562
ROpenSci	563
Rosebud Sioux Tribe	564
Rosebud Sioux Tribe - Sicangu Climate Center	565
Rutgers University	566
Salish Kootenai College	567
San Diego State University	568
SESYNC (National Socio-Environmental Synthesis Center)	569
SIKU	570
Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History	571
Southern California Coastal Water Research Project	572
Southwestern Indian Polytechnic Institute	573
Stony Brook University	574
TCUs	575
Technical University of Munich	576
Tel Aviv University	577
TERN Australia (Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network)	578
Texas A&M University	579
Texas Parks and Wildlife	580
The Carpentries	581
The Living Data Project	582
The Nature Conservancy	583
The Public Knowledge Workshop (NGO, IL)	584
TU Dresden	585
UC Berkeley Data Science & Environment	586
UCAR (University Corporation for Atmospheric Research)	587
UCSB Master of Environmental Data Science (MEDS)	588
UF Florida Institute of Built Environmental Resilience	589
Unidata (UCAR Community Programs)	590
United Tribes Technical College	591

University of Adelaide	592
University of Alabama	593
University of Arizona	594
University of California Berkeley	595
University of California Davis	596
University of California Irvine	597
University of California Santa Barbara	598
University of California Santa Cruz	599
University of Colorado Boulder (CU Boulder)	600
University of Florida	601
University of Guam	602
University of Maine	603
University of Maryland	604
University of Massachusetts Amherst	605
University of Miami	606
University of Michigan	607
University of Montana	608
University of New Mexico	609
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	610
University of Oregon	611
University of Puerto Rico	612
University of Queensland	613
University of Rhode Island	614
University of South Carolina	615
University of Sydney	616
University of Texas at El Paso	617
University of Washington	618
University of Wisconsin-Madison	619
US National Park Service	620
USA-NPN (National Phenology Network)	621
USDA-ARS (Agricultural Research Service)	622
USDA (Beltsville, Maryland, USA)	623
USDA (United States Department of Agriculture)	624
USFS (United States Forest Service)	625
USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station	626
USFWS (US Fish and Wildlife Service)	627
USGS (United States Geological Survey)	628
USGS CASC (Climate Adaptation Science Centers)	629
USGS GBIF-US (Global Biodiversity Information Facility)	630
USGS OBIS-USA (Ocean Biodiversity Information System)	631
USGS Powell Center	632
Water & Tribes Initiative	633
White House Office for Science and Technology Policy (OSTP)	634
Wildlife Insights	635

People working in EDS (n=419)

Abby Benson	Cesar Terrer	Gary McIntyre	Karyn Tabor	Mirko Karan	Simon Cox
Abigail Toretsky	Charles Jason Tinant	Gavin Simpson	Kasandra Lassagne	Monica Turner	Sparkle Malone
Abigail Ward	Charlie Catlett	Gerardo Armendariz	Kat Le	Morgan Ernest	Spencer Clark
Abu Namzaideh	Charuleka Varadharajan	Grant Foster	Kate Thibault	Mostafa Javadian	Stace Beaulieu
Adam Mahood	Chelsea Cook	Gregory Maurer	Kathe Todd-Brown	Mykhailo Rudko	Steven Allison
Adrienne Marshall	Chelsea Nagy	Guthrie Ducheneaux	Katherine Halama	Nancy Emery	Steven Miller
Al Kuslikis	Chris Beirne	Halina Do-Linh Hamidreza	Katherine Siegel	Natalie Mastin	Steven Nerem
Alex Barth	Chris Bretherton	Norouzi	Kathleen Prudic	Natalie Meyers	Sujith Ravi
Alex Rose	Chris Guiterman	Hande Benson	Kathryn McConnell	Natalie Robinson	Sumanta Chatterjee
Alexa Azure	Chris Hakkenberg	Hannah Haynie	Katie Jones	Nathan A. Quarderer	Susan Cook-Patton
Alexey Voinov	Chris Ray	Hannah Zonneville	Kayna Agostini	Nathan Emery	Susan Sullivan
Alicia Foxx	Chris Rezendes	Hao Ye	Keith Krause	Nathan Korinek	Sven Bohms
Alisa Coffin	Christina Grozinger	Hari Prasanna Das	Kel Markert	Natty Rindlaub	Sydne Record
Alison Post	Christine Laney	Haruko Wainwright	Kelly Aho	Naupaka Zimmerman	Tad Dallas
Allan Craig	Cibele Amaral	Helen Sofaer	Kelly Caylor	Nayan Mallick	Tait Weicht
Allison Myers-Pigg	Claire Lunch	Henry Harwood	Kelly Easterday	Nayani Ilangakoon	Tamma Carleton
Alycia Crall	Claire Monteleoni	Hilary Brumberg	Kendi Davies	Nick Haddad	Tawa Ducheneaux
Alyssa Rosemartin	Clinton Francis	Hillary Hull	Kerstin Lehnert	Nick Lyon	TC Chkraborty
Amanda Carr	Cole Kellerer	Hsun-Yi Hsieh	Khum Thapa-Magar	Nico Franz	Ted Haberman
Amanda Hughes	Corey Smith	Ian Pearse	Kimberly Cook	Nicolas Betancourt	Terri Adams
Amanda Richey	Corinna Gries	Isaac Shepard	Kimberly Thompson	Nicole Hemming-Schroeder	Theresa Crimmins
Amanda S. Hering	Courtney Scarborough	Jack Dangermond	Kirk Klausmeyer	Nidhin Harilal	Thomas Martin
Amber Finley	Dan Gavin	Jada Daniels	Kristina Riemer	Nirav Merchant	Thomas Stark
Amber Runyon	Dan Wildcat	James Marquis	Kshitiz Khanal	Nneamaka Uba	Tianshu Lin
Amely Bauer	Dana Chadwick	James Randerson	Kylie Rezendes	Nsalambi Nkongolo	Tiffany Marie Knight
Amy Goldman	Dana Gehring	James Rattling	Kyra Clark-Wolf	Olanrewaju Johnson	Timberley Roane
Ana M. Tarano	Daniel Howard	Leaf	Lala Kounta	Oludunsin Arodudu	Timon Keller
Ananya Roy	Daphne Virlar-Knight	James Stegen	Lara Kueppers	Otis Brown	Tong Liu
Andrea Anteau	Darian Sorenson	Jared Rennie	Laura Dee	Paola Barajas	Tristan Goulden
Andrea Garcia	Dave Calkin	Jason Tinant	Laurel Larsen	Patrick Freeland	Ty Tuff
Andrew Elmore	Dave Jones	Jason West	Leandro Freitas	Patrisse Vasek	Tyler McIntosh
		Jeanette Clark			

Andrew Richardson Aneesh Subramanian Angela Strecker Angela Zhu Ankur Desai Ann Marie Chischilly Anna Boser Anne Gold Antonio Mauro Saraiva Ariel Simons Assaf Anyamba Bailey Murphy Barbara Bomfim Barbara M. Thiers Ben Baiser Ben Halpern Ben Poulter Benjamin Zuckerberg Beryl Morris Bob Newman Bob Rabin Bonnie Meinke Brett Melbourne Brian Gerber Brian Knight Brian Yandell Bridget Hass Caitlin White Cami Griffith Camila Vargas-Poulsen Caren Scott Carl Boettiger Carl Norlen Carlos A. Botero Carmina Gutierrez Carrie Wall	Deb Agarwal Dellena Bloom Dennis Dye Di Yang Diane Srivastava Diego Brizuela Douglas Mbura Dylan Simpson Easton White Edwin Skidmore Eimear M Nic Lughadha EJ Rainville Elie Alhajjar Elisa Girola Elisha Yellow Thunder Elizabeth Hiroyasu Elizabeth Joyner Elizabeth LaRue Ellen Bledsoe Ellen Denny Elsa Culler Emiley Eloe-Fadrosch Emily Biggane Emily Harbo Emily Ward Eric Parrish Eric Sokol Erick Verleye Erin Belval Erin Polka Erin Robinson Esther Rolf Ethan White Eva Kinnebrew Evan Fricke Felipe Montealegre	Jeewantha Bandara Jeff Weber Jeffery Oliver Jennifer Balch Jens-Christian Svenning Jerry Gammie Jessica Burnett Jessica Logan Jessica Matthews Jessica Weidenfeld Jhon Goes In Center Jim Sanovia Jingyi Huang Jinsu Elhance Joan Damerow Joe Miller Joe Scott John Fasullo John Musinsky John Parker John Platt John Sawyer John Zobitz Jonathan Chase Jonathan Pauli Jonathan Sanderman Joni Tobacco Joseph Burant Joseph Yracheta Julia Kelliher Julie Maldonado Julie Padilla Julie Steward-Lowndes Julien Brun Justina White Eyes Kali Dale	Leonard Boussioux Lesley Wyborn Levi Simons Lihui Lydia Zhang Lilly Jones Lindsay Campbell Lise St Denis Liz LaRue Liz Neeley Lizbeth Amador Lola Fatoyinbo Lucas Harris Mansi Shah Margaret Palmer Marie Faust Marina Kogan Marina Wolowski Marisa Mamede Mark Finney Markelle Kelly Martha Anderson Martha Downs Maruthi Sridhar Balaji Bhaskar Matt Kane Matt Rossi Matthew Jones Matthew Pearce Max Cook Megan Cattau Megan Littrell Megan Mills-Novoa Melanie Kammerer Melissa Lucash Michael Binford Michael Gavin Michael Packard	Paul Choi Paula Mabee Peter Isaac Philimon Two Eagle Philip Robertson Phoebe Zarnetske Rachel Meyer Randy Swaty Raphael Apeaning Raphel Mazor Rebecca Batchelor Reginald Blake Rena F. Brown Rob Guralnick Rob Redmon Robert Hensley Robert Newman Robin Omalley Rodrigo Leite Ronan Foley Ronit Purian Roshelle Pederson Ruben Remelgado Ruby L. Leung Rud Platt Rupert Seidl Ruth Oliver Ruth Plenty Sweetgrass-She Kills Sally Wang Samantha Csik Sandy Sum Sara Beery Sara Paull Sarah Elmendorf Sarah Stone Saumya Sinha	Tyson Swetnam Tzahi Y. Cath Valentin Stefan Van Butsic Veronica Southerland Virginia Iglesias Wai Ho CHAK Werner Rammer Will Wieder Xingchao Chen Xingyuan Chen Yang Li Yang Zhang Yasmin Tavares Yuhan Rao Yun Qian Yun Yang Zhe Feng
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Carsten Meyer	Feng Gao	Karen C. Short	Michael Wurm	Scott Jasechko
Casey Jenson	Firouzeh Taghikhah	Karen Cozzetto	Michele Cosi	Scotty Strachan
Cassie Buhler	Foster Sawyer	Karen Short	Mike Dietze	Shana Sundstrum
Catherine Hulshof	Francisco J. Guerrero	Karena Yan	Mike Koontz	Shashi Konduri
Catherine Jarnevich	Frannie Monasterio	Kari Segraves	Miles Moore	Shelby Weis
Catherine O'Reilly	Gabriel Abreu-Vigil	Karin Riley	Millie Chapman	Siddeswara Guru
Cathleen Torres Parisian	Garrett Knowlton	Karthik Balaguru	Ming Posa	Sigal Kaplan